

INTEGRATED SEQUESTRATION

Design Research Into Utilising Enhanced Rock Weathering for Architecture

ANDREAS KOERNER

University of Innsbruck, University College London
andreas.koerner.at@gmail.com

ANETE KRISTA SALMANE

University College London
a.salmane@ucl.ac.uk

KEYWORDS

Weathering; Materials, Surface Roughness, Carbon Sequestration, System Design

ABSTRACT

Enhanced Rock Weathering (ERW) offers a promising strategy for climate change mitigation by accelerating natural rock weathering to capture and store atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂). Parallel to a comprehensive state-of-the-art review of ERW and the parameters relevant to architecture, this study investigates the subject through a mixed method of environmental simulations, material explorations and prototype fabrication. ERW's effectiveness depends on maximising surface area for interaction between Ca- and Mg-rich rocks and atmospheric CO₂, typically achieved using rock powder. This research proposes a method to embed wollastonite and basalt particles in architectural fabric, activating these urban surfaces. A modular hexagonal system is designed to increase CO₂ interaction by extending the surface flow of rainwash. The concept is evaluated using computational fluid dynamics simulations and laboratory material tests to identify parameters for water flow rate and material porosity. The findings offer insights into the potential of architectural surfaces to sequester atmospheric carbon, laying the groundwork for further quantification of carbon uptake.

1. INTRODUCTION

Enhanced Rock Weathering (ERW) offers a promising strategy for climate change mitigation by accelerating natural rock weathering to capture and store atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂). According to the UN, solutions to mitigate embodied carbon emissions, like materials and construction, lag behind those concerning operational emissions (United Nations, 2023). Tackling this issue effectively requires global action and collaboration, uniting stakeholders from every stage of the building sector's lifecycle. In response, the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) outline seventeen goals for a more sustainable future, strongly affecting the construction industry, urban planning, and architecture (Ramsgaard Thomsen and Miller, 2020; RIBA, 2019).

Decarbonisation and adapting to future climates are key aspects of this transition. While technological innovation can reduce carbon emissions (Wiedmann et al., 2020), sequestering atmospheric carbon through low-tech, high-impact methods shows further potential. This paper documents research on a strategy for CO₂ sequestration by utilising existing vertical surfaces in urban environments. ERW strategies are translated from agriculture to buildings, presenting a novel micro-to-macro method for long-term carbon sequestration using modelling, simulation, fabrication, and design. In addition to ERW, complementary biochemical weathering processes can further help to approach carbon neutrality.

1.1. ENHANCED ROCK WEATHERING

Natural rock weathering is a slow geological process, taking centuries. In architecture, weathering conventionally means the natural environment's detrimental impact on building surfaces over time (Mostafavi and Leatherbarrow, 1993). ERW is an inorganic carbon dioxide removal (CDR) method that accelerates natural CO₂ sequestration processes by amending substrates with certain aggregates (Kantzas et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022). Applications of the method frequently rely on spreading crushed silicate minerals on agricultural soils, allowing the high surface area to interact with the CO₂ dissolved in rainwater (te Pas et al., 2023). In the process, atmospheric carbon is sequestered in the form of carbonates and prevented from returning to the atmosphere for centuries (Figure 1). The weathering process is influenced by chemical, physical, and biological variables (Deng et al., 2023), with cascading effects on the soil and aquatic ecosystems.

In recent years, a range of studies have been performed to model and estimate the potential of this carbon removal strategy using variables such as governmental policies, geospatial data, and efficiency rates (Beerling et al., 2020; Deng et al., 2023). While the technology is promising, it is highly variable in its efficiency and lacks standardised quantification methods.

Figure 1: Conceptual comparison between natural rock weathering (left) and enhanced rock weathering in agricultural contexts (middle) and cementitious materials (right). The thick line represents the exposed surface area that can react with rainwash.

Currently, the focus for implementing ERW is on agricultural applications where large areas allow for scaling (Reershemius et al., 2023). From an ecological perspective, urban environments offer much potential: a significant vertical surface area remains biologically inert (Parker and Cruz, 2023). The ongoing research presented in this paper explores an alternative context for ERW by embedding crushed silicate rocks in architectural elements, thus enabling large unused surface areas to become biogeochemically active (Figure 2). ERW approaches are not without risk, and their effectiveness varies depending on geographic location and environmental context (Choi et al., 2021; Eufrazio et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022). Existing research on integrating CDR or Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) in architecture often relies on adding mechanical devices or other structures to buildings (Bryan and Ben Salamah, 2018; Eberhardt, 2023). Therefore, this research investigates the integration of ERW as a carbon sequestration method in buildings, specifically cementitious façade elements with various aggregates.

1.2. AIMS & CHALLENGES

Using digital design tools and advanced materials, we can create environmentally active and performative architectural surfaces to help cities adapt to climate change challenges. ERW is taking place parallel to concrete carbonation, exhibiting overlapping effects. While this poses a challenge for monitoring and quantification, the carbonation process in concrete is relatively well studied, especially when looking at the depth of the material's chemical change over time. To try to delineate the two processes, it is important to assess the depth of rainfall penetration and residence time in the material and the timescale of the change. Furthermore, once the carbon dynamics have been quantified, a life cycle assessment (LCA) is required to assess the

environmental impacts of the material and system. While the question of whether the sequestered CO₂ offsets the initial CO₂ emissions caused by construction is beyond the scope of this research, it must remain central to future studies. The aim – to activate architectural surfaces for ERW in urban environments in response to the climate crisis – is investigated through a workflow (Figure 3) consisting of material testing, simulations, and design research.

Figure 2:
Conceptual framework of ERW integration in the urban fabric.

2. METHODOLOGY

Parallel to a comprehensive state-of-the-art review of ERW and the parameters relevant to architecture, this study explores the subject through a mixed method of environmental simulation, prototype fabrication, and laboratory testing. The micro-to-macro investigation, utilising prototyping/making and computational design framework, is novel or ERW research. The concept is evaluated using CFD simulations (Figures 6 and 7) and laboratory material tests (Figure 9) to identify parameters for water flow rate and aggregate composition. The former analyses local shear stress (geometry-dependent friction) and fluid velocity (diverting water flow). The latter analyses the depth of carbon uptake into the material to provide data for impact assessment.

2.1. PROTOTYPING (ELEMENTS)

Wollastonite and basalt were selected as suitable silicate minerals based on the comparatively high CO₂ capture in ERW laboratory scale studies and corresponding data availability (Knapp et al., 2023; te Pas et al., 2023). A range of material formulations was tested, varying the ratios of basalt (0-2mm), fine grain silica sand (0.25-0.5mm), and wollastonite (fine powder) aggregates within a white Portland cement

matrix to develop a porous yet structurally stable material for casting (Table 1).

Each batch was supplemented with a small amount of polymer reinforcement fibres. These initial material tests were used to identify promising formulations through qualitative assessment methods such as workability, casting behaviour, and visual inspection of casted elements. In further steps, surface roughness and porosity were assessed using a VHX-7000 digital microscope (Figure 9).

Figure 3: Key contributing factors for enhanced rock weathering (ERW) integration in architectural contexts, contrasted with natural weathering processes. The grey box represents the workflow and scope of this research.

	Cement	Water	Aggregate breakdown		
			Sand	Wollastonite	Basalt
S	1	0.5-0.75	0.5-1		
W	1	0.5-1		0.5-1	
B	1	0.5			0.5-0.8
S+W	1	0.6-1	1	0.2-1	
S+B	1	0.5-1	1		0.2-1
S+W+B	1	1.2	1.2	0.2	0.2

Table 1: Summary of the tested material formulations expressed in ratio by volume (Cement=1). Bold indicated the values relevant to section 3.2.

As part of the design research process, a parametric system of modular elements was created using digital design techniques. It consists of a limited number of modules with varying volume-to-surface-area ratios, and variation is achieved through rotation and iteration (Figure 4). Prototypes of the elements were fabricated through casting (Figure 5).

Figure 4:
 A limited number of modules, arranged in a hexagonal grid to increase the volume-to-surface-area ratio. In cm^2/m^3 for depicted elements:
 0.=296/360, 1.=282/330,
 2.=133/241, 3.=132/266,
 4.=133/258, 5.=133/243,
 6.=133/238, 7.=283/351.

Figure 5:
 One of seven different elements fabricated through casting.

2.2. DESIGN WORKFLOW (AGGREGATION)

Informed by computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, a hexagonal system was designed to increase rainwater-surface interaction and minimise evaporation. Given an existing façade condition, the flow of rainwater is analysed (Figure 6). Based on the information gained, the workflow foresees the allocation of obstacles (elements) that further slow the flow and increase the exposure of ERW-active surfaces to the dissolved carbon in the water (Figure 7). In the parametric design environment (Maxon Cinema 4D), the CFD simulation's graphic output (image map) is responsible for the selection of elements (Figure 8). Each element represents a different geometry and a different material mix. According to the location in the grid, this affects the diversion of rainwater flows (Figures 6 and 7) and the corresponding carbon uptake based on the embedded silica minerals (Table 1 and Figure 4).

Figure 6: The geometry-dependent rainwash distribution on a façade informs the selection of elements based on a parametric workflow.

Figure 7: Computational fluid dynamics simulations to evaluate rainwash velocity and distribution. Solar radiation can be considered to assess bio-receptivity potentials.

3. FINDINGS

When reviewing the prototyping and digital design investigations, the findings of three aspects appear most relevant. 1) The material studies indicate that mineral choice affects the casting and ERW performance. However, the latter remains to be verified in future studies. 2) Based on the literature review, integrating ERW strategies into vertical surfaces in urban environments appears promising to lower embodied carbon emissions of buildings. 3) Complimentary biological weathering mechanisms can further enhance the impact of ERW in architecture while offering novel design attributes and aesthetics.

Figure 8: Digital design workflow based on CFD images and image maps: A limited number of modules arranged in a hexagonal grid to increase the volume-to-surface-area ratio.

3.1. MATERIAL STUDIES

Each set of material tests aimed to lower the water and increase the aggregate ratio to enhance the surface roughness and porosity. Generally, it was observed that it was possible to achieve a lower water ratio with basalt compared to wollastonite aggregate, presumably due to the larger aggregate size. This iterative approach allowed mixture refinement, laying the groundwork for subsequent quantitative evaluations of physical properties and material interactions with rainwater. The process ensured that selected material compositions would be fabricable and functionally viable for architectural use. Advanced fabrication techniques like additive manufacturing with functional grading (Figure 4) could help scale ERW strategies for larger architectural surfaces.

Microscopic examination of the sand, basalt, and wollastonite material revealed a high fidelity in replicating the intricate surface details of the 3D-printed positive used to create the mould (Figure 9).

The material exhibited microporosity, exposing the silicate aggregates, alongside macroscopic porosity resulting from the casting process and

the water ratio of the mix. While the materials' surface is the primary feature interacting with rainwater, it is crucial to understand how the material performs in bulk. Therefore, the selected samples from initial tests should undergo porosimetry analysis.

Figure 9: Microscopic image of basalt aggregate in the cement matrix (left). The surface details of the sand, basalt, and wollastonite material and the cross-section depict the surface roughness (right).

While concrete is often referred to as an inert material, chemical interactions occur in the material beyond the 28-day curing time. Examples include carbonation, sulfate attack and hydration (Taylor, 1997; Chang and Chen, 2006). These processes and chemical reactions demonstrate that concrete as a material undergoes continuous changes influenced by the environmental conditions, material and geometry design. Even though many of these processes are primarily seen as disadvantageous, by introducing ERW mechanisms we approach the material as transformative (simultaneously subtractive and additive) in its nature. The continuous weathering of the silicate aggregates increases the material's porosity while depositing Ca- and Mg- carbonates within the cementitious material pores or cavities or washing these newly formed particles away. Furthermore, construction activities generally increase the abundance of silicate minerals rich in Ca and Mg. It has been shown that anthropogenic soils containing demolition waste exhibit higher rates of carbonate formations and atmospheric CO₂ capture due to the abundance of these minerals (Washbourne et al., 2012).

3.2. ENHANCING THE APPLICATION POTENTIAL OF ERW

With the projected increases in the world's population, extensive urban areas have become a global phenomenon. Integrating ERW in architecture can help create more sustainable urban environments while adhering to the strategies outlined in the SDGs. Cities provide much inert surface area on façades. Strategically covering dormant surfaces with chemically active materials, such as the ones developed for this study, can potentially increase CCS rates. A study by Dupla et al. (2024) has shown that 20 tons of basalt per hectare is feasible in agriculture. When considering the according 2kg/m² as a rule-of-thumb, one can calculate the ERW potential for urban environments given their vertical surface area and local environmental parameters like average annual precipitation. Evaluating the design framework

and prototypes presented here, we can apply this value to the average volume (190 cm^3) of the eight elements in this study (Figure 4) and the upper limit of the wet-mix (B) basalt ratio (Table 1) of roughly 25%. We can then take the average material volume of aggregated elements ($156 \text{ pieces} = 29640 \text{ cm}^3$) on one m^2 in the design framework into account. Assuming the average density of basalt as $2.9\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$, we arrive at 7410 cm^3 , equalling 21 kg per m^2 . This ratio is tenfold higher than in Dupla et al.'s (2024) study. Consequently, future research can rely on a lower basalt ratio in the wet mixes while exploring means to achieve higher silica aggregate concentrations on the outer surface of the exposed elements (Figure 4). However, two aspects remain unanswered by this study and must be investigated: How does the material porosity affect carbon sequestration in the agricultural and architectural contexts? How does the dry weight of basalt/wollastonite after curing affect the ratios?

Figure 10:
Full-scale design descriptor of a modular system for integrating ERW into architecture. The varying shades of grey indicate different material mixes (Table 1): lighter = wollastonite; darker = basalt.

The developed design method facilitates control over the flow rates and distribution of rainwash over surfaces. Therefore, ERW-active compounds containing wollastonite and basalt aggregates can be strategically placed to maximise their impact. The created design descriptor helps to visualise and test larger aggregations of elements (Figure 10). While the material mixes' actual CO₂ uptake requires further laboratory and long-term in-situ testing, the literature research has shown that integrating ERW in architecture for carbon sequestration shows significant potential regarding the available surface area. The investigated low-tech, high-impact CCS strategy furthermore investigates technology already accessible to the construction industry, such as the use of advanced cementitious materials, digital environmental simulations, parametric design, prototyping, and material testing.

3.3. COMPLEMENTARY BIOLOGICAL MECHANISMS

While integrating geochemical processes within the fabric of our built environment is one avenue, biochemical weathering is a complementary process crucial to design to maximise the impact of carbon sequestration via surfaces of the built environment. The interactions of microorganisms and their surrounding environments are an underexplored source of strategies that could be deployed against climate change. A better understanding of the impact of the various material mixes (Table 1) on the bio-receptivity of surfaces could help create hospitable environments for such non-human lifeforms. Recently, a prominent collective of microbiologists has published a call for immediate action to deploy microbial solutions against climate catastrophe across many applied microbiology platforms and journals globally (Peixoto et al., 2024). Microbial enhancement of carbon sequestration is one of the six strategies proposed in the document. Microbes play a significant role in the biogeochemical cycling and element biotransformations that regulate the availability of life-sustaining resources in the terrestrial “critical zone” (Gadd, 2010). A range of metabolic activities such as organic acid secretion, redox reactions, chelation effects, enzymatic reactions and others allow microorganisms to mine substrates for metals and other compounds. In the context of ERW, carbonic anhydrase enzymes have been explored due to their ability to increase naturally occurring dissolution rates of CO₂ in water (Peplow, 2023). Carbonic anhydrases are ubiquitous enzymes that catalyse the reversible hydration of CO₂ [$\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} \leftrightarrow \text{H}^+ + \text{HCO}_3^-$], increasing the concentrations required for silicate mineral dissolution and, thus, carbon sequestration. Field studies of industrially produced carbonic anhydrase supplements to ERW are currently underway. However, the enzymes could also be secreted in situ by a range of organisms, such as plants, algae, cyanobacteria and bacteria found in soil and on natural or man-made surfaces (Moroney et al., 2001; Xiao et al., 2015).

3.4. CHALLENGES

Despite the emerging knowledge about ERW applications in agricultural environments, confidently assessing the scaled-up efficiency and safety of this process still faces considerable challenges. ERW involves highly complex biogeochemical interactions influenced by environmental factors such as temperature, precipitation, soil composition, and microbial activity, making predictive modelling and monitoring difficult (Edwards et al., 2017). This complexity and the myriad of parameters that influence the weathering process lead to challenges in standardisation and reliable quantitative methodologies for the evaluation of CO₂ sequestration potential both in the laboratory and in field studies. Additionally, to determine if the process is environmentally beneficial overall, it is important to account for all raw materials' embodied emissions and other impact categories. Cement manufacturing, sourcing, and processing the fine particle silica rock are associated with high energy and resource demands (Müller et al., 2014). Understanding the lifetime of the basalt and wollastonite-supplemented concrete mixes is crucial to evaluating the net environmental impact. Furthermore, digital simulations require comparable laboratory and in-situ testing for verification.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary results presented in this paper, alongside the design framework, provide a foundation for future collaborations with industry and academia to advance ERW applications in architecture to develop carbon-neutral, even carbon-negative, design solutions. For example, interdisciplinary knowledge exchange can help to implement ERW methods from agriculture into architecture, utilising the available vertical surfaces. Selected material formulations should be exposed outdoors to quantify carbonate minerals' precipitation and estimate CO₂ capture. To holistically evaluate how these elements perform across time and whether the initially emitted CO₂ is offset across time, further test data is required for LCA. Furthermore, due to the variability of the results, LCA could also be used as a predictive tool for forecasting and comparing multiple scenarios depending on time, future climate, and geographic location.

While this research investigated an inorganic micro-to-macro method for long-term carbon sequestration through ERW, controlling rainwash flow and material porosity can also increase the bio-receptivity of cementitious surfaces (Cruz and Beckett, 2016). Biogenic weathering of minerals is an under-explored yet important contributor to natural and enhanced rock weathering due to the intricate metabolic processes that microorganisms play at the interface of the mineral surfaces and their environment (Wild et al., 2022). Combining inorganic ERW with bio-integrated processes can potentially increase the carbon uptake of buildings while creating more resilient, greener, and responsive cities. Digital design methodologies, advanced fabrication, and

additive manufacturing can help to generate complex architectural systems that functionally allocate (grade) material performances. While this paper explored additive manufacturing for low-tech mould making, more advanced techniques could help automate the specific materialisation of parametric models, which would help scale the processes for increased impact.

REFERENCES

- Beerling, D.J., Kantzas, E.P., Lomas, M.R. et al., 2020, Potential for large-scale CO₂ removal via enhanced rock weathering with croplands. *Nature* 583: 7815, pp. 242–248.
- Bryan, H. and Ben Salamah, F., 2018, Building-integrated Carbon Capture: Development of an Appropriate and Applicable Building-integrated System for Carbon Capture and Shade. *Civil Engineering and Architecture* 6(3), pp. 155–163.
- Chang, C.F., and Jing-Wen C., 2006, The experimental investigation of concrete carbonation depth. *Cement and Concrete Research* 36(9), pp. 1760-1767.
- Choi, W.J., Park, H.J., Cai, Y. et al., 2021, Environmental Risks in Atmospheric CO₂ Removal Using Enhanced Rock Weathering Are Overlooked. *Environmental Science & Technology* 55(14), pp. 9627–9629.
- Cruz, M. and Beckett, R., 2016, Bioreceptive Design: A Novel Approach to Biodigital Materiality. *Architectural Research Quarterly* 20(1), pp. 51–64.
- Deng, H., Sonnenthal, E., Arora, B. et al., 2023, The environmental controls on efficiency of enhanced rock weathering in soils. *Scientific reports* 13(1): 9765.
- Dupla, X. et al., 2024, Let the dust settle: Impact of enhanced rock weathering on soil biological, physical, and geochemical fertility. *Science of The Total Environment* 954: 176297.
- Eberhardt, E., 2023, Heirloom opens first large-scale carbon capture plant in US.[online] Available at: <<https://www.dezeen.com/2023/11/15/heirloom-opens-first-large-scale-commercial-carbon-capture-plant-in-us/>> [Accessed 4 October 2024].
- Edwards, D.P. et al., 2017, Climate change mitigation: potential benefits and pitfalls of enhanced rock weathering in tropical agriculture. *Biology letters* 13(4): 20160715.
- Eufrazio, R.M., Kantzas, E.P., Edwards, N.R. et al., 2022, Environmental and health impacts of atmospheric CO₂ removal by enhanced rock weathering depend on nations' energy mix. *Communications Earth & Environment* 3(1).
- Gadd, G.M., 2010, Metals, minerals and microbes: Geomicrobiology and bioremediation. *Microbiology* 156(3), pp. 609-643.

- Kantzas, E.P., Val Martin, M., Lomas, M.R. et al., 2022, Substantial carbon drawdown potential from enhanced rock weathering in the United Kingdom. *Nature Geoscience* 15(5), pp. 382–389.
- Knapp, W.J., Stevenson, E.I., Renforth, P. et al., 2023, Quantifying CO₂ Removal at Enhanced Weathering Sites: a Multiproxy Approach. *Environmental Science & Technology* 57(26), pp. 9854–9864.
- Moroney, J. V., Bartlett, S. G., and Samuelsson, G., 2001, Carbonic anhydrases in plants and algae. *Plant, Cell & Environment* 24(2), pp. 141-153.
- Mostafavi, M., and Leatherbarrow, D., 1993, *On Weathering: Life of Buildings in Time*. Cambridge: The MIT Press.
- Müller, H.S., Haist, M. and Vogel, M., 2014, Assessment of the sustainability potential of concrete and concrete structures considering their environmental impact, performance and lifetime. *Construction and Building Materials* 67, pp.321-337.
- Parker, B. and Cruz, M., 2023, Symbiotic Tectonics of the Biocene. In: Pardal, C. and Corbat, E., eds. *Integrative Façades: Everything that can happen between inside and outside*. Málaga: Recolectores Urbanos Editorial, pp. 152–161.
- Peixoto, R., Voolstra, C.R., Stein, L.Y. et al., 2024, Microbial solutions must be deployed against climate catastrophe. *Nature Communications* (15): 9637.
- Peplow, M., 2024, Enzymes boost ‘rock weathering’ to trap CO₂ in soil. *Nature Biotechnology* 42(9), pp. 1326-1328.
- Ramsgaard Thomsen, M. and Miller, N.M., 2020, *An Architecture Guide to the UN 17 Sustainable Development Goals*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.uia-architectes.org/en/resource/architecture-guide-to-the-un-17-sustainable-development-goals-english/>> [Accessed 2 December 2023].
- Reershemius, T., Kelland, M.E., Jordan, J.S. et al., 2023, Initial Validation of a Soil-Based Mass-Balance Approach for Empirical Monitoring of Enhanced Rock Weathering Rates. *Environmental Science & Technology* 57(48): pp. 19497–19507.
- Royal Institute of British Architects, 2019, *UN Sustainable Development Goals in Practice*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.architecture.com/knowledge-and-resources/resources-landing-page/un-sustainable-development-goals-in-practice>> [Accessed 12 December 2022]

- Taylor, H.F.W., 1997, Cement chemistry. London: Thomas Telford.
- te Pas, E.E.E.M., Hagens, M. and Comans, R.N.J., 2023, Assessment of the enhanced weathering potential of different silicate minerals to improve soil quality and sequester CO₂. *Frontiers in Climate* 4.
- United Nations Environment Programme, Yale Center for Ecosystems + Architecture, 2023, Building Materials and the Climate: Constructing a New Future.[online] Available at: <<https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/43293>> [Accessed 12 December 2024]
- Washbourne, C.L., Renforth, P., and Manning, D.A.C., 2012, Investigating carbonate formation in urban soils as a method for capture and storage of atmospheric carbon. *Science of the total environment* 431, pp. 166-175.
- Wiedmann, T., Lenzen, M., Keyßer, L.T. et al., 2020, Scientists' Warning on Affluence. *Nature Communications* 11(1): 3107.
- Wild, B., Gerrits, R. and Bonneville, S., 2022, The contribution of living organisms to rock weathering in the critical zone. *npj Materials Degradation* 6(1).
- Xiao, L. et al., 2015, Effect of carbonic anhydrase on silicate weathering and carbonate formation at present day CO₂ concentrations compared to primordial values. *Scientific reports* 5(1): 7733.
- Zhang, S., Planavsky, N.J., Katchinoff, J. et al., 2022, River chemistry constraints on the carbon capture potential of surficial enhanced rock weathering. *Limnology and Oceanography* 67(S2).